

Student evaluation and feedback on the topic

At the end of our first semester, we asked students for feedback on the MM project. At the start of the year, when they were asked their opinions about using marijuana as a treatment for various ailments, approximately 75% of them said that this shouldn't be allowed as it was a gateway drug and very dangerous. However, the comments after the project seemed to show that the topic was well received and that they learnt not just about MM, but also to be more open and more critical of the status quo.

Final thoughts

As tutors, through tackling this topic, we learned that we shouldn't be afraid of introducing controversial topics and students do respond well if such projects are scaffolded with care. If you decide to use a controversial topic in your teaching, we suggest that you use the following steps:

1. Include unconscious bias training.
2. Introduce alternative cultural perspectives in a non-threatening environment and manner.
3. Use a range of materials and sources to present a balanced view of the controversial issue.
4. Use and continue to build your own cultural awareness of your students' backgrounds to approach the topic sensitively.

The above steps outline how inclusivity can be achieved through topic choices which acculturate (IFY) students to specific academic and western cultural expectations, conventions and requirements through guided practice and the creation of 'safe spaces' for overcoming 'learning shock'. Acculturation should be possible with any international student cohort, not just IFY students, using these steps but be mindful to monitor your own potential unconscious bias and be prepared to accept and respect your students' newly informed cultural choices at the end of the project, whatever they are.

References

- Aljurj et al.** (2020). Exploring academic dishonesty in the Middle East: a qualitative analysis of students' perceptions. *Studies in Higher Education*. 45 (7), 1461–1473.
- BBC.** (2018). Alfie Dingley 'Amazingly Well' After Cannabis Treatment. The BBC. [Online]. 27 October. [Accessed 11 July 2022]. Available from: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-coventry-warwickshire-46002763>
- Beauchamp, T. & Childress, J.F.** (2009). *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*. 6th ed. Oxford University Press.
- Cannabiz.** (2021). *Professor Michael Barnes: Global Medical Cannabis Expert, Educator + Advocate*. [Online]. [Accessed 11 July 2022]. Available from: <https://www.cannabizmd.com/profiles/professor-michael-barnes-global-medical-cannabis-expert-educator-advocate/>
- Cannigma.** (2022). *Where is cannabis legal in Asia?* [Online]. [Accessed 11 July 2022]. Available from: <https://cannigma.com/where-cannabis-is-legal-in-asia/>
- Debnath, N.** (2017). Charlie Gard Case: Eammon Holmes and Nick Firth clash over life support ruling. *Express*. [Online]. 12 April. [Accessed 11 July 2022]. Available from: <https://www.express.co.uk/showbiz/tv-radio/790989/Charlie-Gard-case-Eamonn-Holmes-Nick-Ferrari-life-support-ITV-This-Morning>
- Gupta, S.** (2015). *Decriminalise it – Jersey*. [Online]. [Accessed 7 July 2022]. Available from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-SZzgyXhJI>
- Stazicker, A. & Woods, N.** (2022). *Teaching International Foundation Year: A Practical Guide for EAP Practitioners in Higher and Further Education*. Routledge.

Starting the discussion about discrimination in science with international foundation students

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Dr Helena Reis Batalha
INTO UEA LLP, Biology and
Human Physiology module leader
h.batalha@uea.ac.uk

Importance of EDI training for undergraduates

EDI (equality/equity, diversity and inclusivity) awareness is increasingly recognised as important for successful progression through higher education for students, and later on for both employers and employees in the workplace. Being able to navigate a diverse world and collaborate with different team members is critical for student success, especially when many course assignments rely on group work (Koenig et al., 2013). Students are also encouraged to develop soft skills which are essential in today's workplace, and teamwork is in strong demand (Ritter et al., 2018). Consequently, EDI training is being embedded in many undergraduate and foundation programmes across the UK, often in the form of workshops or single day training courses (Miah et al., 2020; Jones et al., 2022).

Context

On the INTO University of East Anglia International Foundation Pathway in Pharmacy, Health & Life Sciences students mainly aim to progress towards health care and life science degrees. Coming from all over the world, our students have grown up in societies with different cultural and academic backgrounds to the UK. The Preparation for Health and Life Sciences module was developed to address

the gap between students' educational backgrounds and the requirements to enter a UK higher education institution. In this context, a series of exploratory, discussion-based seminars about current issues in science and society has been developed for life science students. One of them encourages students to explore the controversial topic of discrimination in science.

This seminar aimed to start the conversation and raise awareness about race and gender discrimination in the scientific world. Facilitating free small group discussion encourages the expression of opinions and feelings about an emotional topic, without the need to reach a consensus (Kitchen, 2012). Thus the seminar was run in a semi-structured conversational style, and allowed all students to express and discuss their views on the subject in a non-judgemental atmosphere. During the seminar, students raised points that were further discussed with their peers, and observation, reflection and critical thinking were encouraged rather than memorisation of concepts, as this promotes deep learning, the development of team and communication skills, and formation of opinions (Cottrell, 2017). Student written reflections, following the Gibbs reflection model (Gibbs, 1998), as well as comments and attitudes in class, were used to evaluate the perceived value of this seminar.

Figure 1: Countries of origin of students participating in the discrimination in science seminar in 2021 and 2022. From left to right: Panama, Albania, Kuwait, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Myanmar, Indonesia, Vietnam, Hong Kong, Japan. Created with <https://www.mapchart.net>

Method – the seminar

The students in the seminar had worked together throughout the year, so knew each other well and were able to interact harmoniously. They were aged 16–24, although most were 18, and came mainly from Asian countries (Figure 1).

Before the seminar, the students were required to watch the movie 'Hidden Figures', about discrimination in science (Table 1). During the seminar, the students were joined online by a guest speaker, closer to their age group, a Cape Verdean ecology researcher doing her PhD in Japan. Being a female scientist of African descent, she provided her perspective by recalling her experiences in the academic world.

At the beginning of the seminar the students and the guest speaker were asked by the moderator to introduce themselves, and to share their impressions about the movie. As groups of students were small, during the seminar each student was invited by name to participate, thereby allowing less confident or fluent individuals to express their opinions. They were asked to describe any type of discrimination they might have observed in their countries. Students, the moderator and the guest could expand and follow up on points that raised interest, and ask further

questions to each other. The students were asked to think specifically about discrimination in science, how discrimination can impact wellbeing, and how diversity can benefit science. They were not lectured on any topic but questioned for clarity when they expressed unconventional views (eg "there is no racism in my country").

During the seminar, participants were shown a short racism-related video entitled 'Doll test – The effects of racism on children' (Table 1). Again, the students and guest speaker were asked to express their feelings and reflections on the video. Finally, the students and the guest speaker were invited to propose and discuss ways to minimise discrimination in the workplace and contribute to a more diverse and inclusive society.

Table 1: Videos watched by the students before and during the seminar on discrimination in science.

	Hidden Figures	Doll test - The effects of racism on children
Created by	Theodore Melfi, Fox 2000 Pictures	Fanpage.it
Available via	Box of Broadcasts	YouTube
Visualisation	Before the seminar	During the seminar
Topic	This 2016 Hollywood movie is loosely based on the stories of Katherine Johnson, Mary Jackson and Dorothy Vaughan, female scientists at NASA in the 1960s, highlighting the gender and race discrimination they faced	Test created to assess the effects of segregation in African-American children, by asking them questions about a black and a white doll, adapted here to Italian children.

Results

All students that watched the movie "Hidden Figures" claimed to enjoy it (Figure 2). Some mentioned being nervous before the seminar for fear of saying the 'wrong' thing but all responded when given opportunity to participate. All students in both years shared stories, issues and/or perceived lack of race discrimination in their country. All students interacted with the moderator (Figure 2), either spontaneously or when prompted, and most students interacted with the guest speaker and each other as well, by asking each other or answering questions.

Some students expressed surprise at learning that racism is still an issue, particularly within the scientific community, while others said they were already aware. Some students see themselves as part of a minority while studying in the UK and recounted incidents of abuse towards Asians during the pandemic; they reflected that being part of a minority might adversely affect their studies or career. Some students claimed that they did not notice discrimination based on race in their countries, and proposed reasons for this, such as being from very small countries with very

homogenous communities, and not many people from different races or ethnic groups being present (eg Kosovo, Vietnam).

Some students proposed historical reasons driving systemic racism. Some were aware of discrimination against ethnic or religious minorities in their countries and believe this is a bigger problem than race-based discrimination. Students highlighted greater awareness of sexism than racism in society as this is something they observed within their own families. Some mentioned how their mothers had to work harder than men, including their fathers, to advance in their careers. Such comments were made by both male and female students.

Some students realised they sometimes unconsciously discriminate against people, and said the seminar made them more aware of this. Others reflected that, in addition to striving to overcome this and be more inclusive, they should help where necessary through being an ally in such struggles.

All students reported enjoying the discrimination seminar, none made offensive remarks and none reported feeling offended during or after the seminar.

Discussion and conclusion

To summarise, this was the first time that some students talked about racism in science, and the first time some reflected on discrimination in their home country. There was some discussion about other forms of discrimination (see Results). Most students recognised this is still an important issue in society and expressed the wish for this to be taught in schools and/or discussed more often. Overall, students demonstrated an increased awareness of discrimination issues in society by the end of the seminar.

Using a Hollywood movie to start the seminar contributed to creating an informal atmosphere and facilitated the start of what might otherwise be an uncomfortable discussion. It also illustrated how discrimination, a potentially abstract topic for some students, affects lives of real people and science development in general (Graves et al., 2022; Woolston, 2021). Using a guest participant with a different background and experiences to the seminar moderator was an attempt to reinforce the positive message that diversity is valuable; importantly, this contributed to the informal and relaxed feel of

Figure 2: Percentage student preparation work for the seminar (watching the movie 'Hidden Figures'), attendance and participation, and optional written reflections (between a choice of four different seminars), in both years. A total of eight students participated in the first year and seven in the second.

the session. Students agreed having a guest speaker helped them get another perspective and they enjoyed learning from her experiences.

Discussions about racism and discrimination in science have the potential to be uncomfortable and controversial. It is however important to raise awareness, as the students will encounter these issues in the future, including in their workplace, and it is important to start open-minded, impartial discussions about the topic. Seminars are a good way to do this as they enhance inclusivity in the classroom (Figure 3). By asking students to report personal observations, a more neutral, non-judgemental backdrop is created in which to have these discussions. It is critical to make sure there are no right or wrong answers; when a student makes an unexpected observation or remark we can simply ask why – if anything this will encourage further reflection. A dialogue can start and, by not having a fixed learning objective, creates the possibility for students to develop their opinions and place in society (McArthur, 2022). Observation, reflection and discussion open the door to heightened awareness and, hopefully, encourage attitudes that minimise discrimination, in the scientific world and in society in general.

Figure 3: Multiple ways in which seminars can enhance inclusivity for students. Inspired by Ruggs et al., 2012, and Greer, 2014.

References

Cottrell, S. (2017). *Critical thinking skills: effective analysis, argument and reflection*. Palgrave.

Gibbs, G. (1988). *Learning by doing: A guide to teaching and learning methods*. Further Education Unit.

Graves Jr, J. L., Kearney, M., Barabino, G., & Malcom, S. (2022). Inequality in science and the case for a new agenda. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(10), e2117831119.

Greer, A. (2014). Increasing Inclusivity in the Classroom. Vanderbilt University Center for Teaching. Retrieved [22/12/2022] from <https://cft.vanderbilt.edu/guides-sub-pages/increasing-inclusivity-in-the-classroom/>

Jones, L., Sarju, J. P., Dessent, C. E. H., Matharu, A. S., & Smith, D. K. (2022). What Makes a Professional Chemist? Embedding Equality, Diversity,

and Inclusion into Chemistry Skills Training for Undergraduates. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 99(1), 480–486. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jchemed.1c00500

Kitchen, M. (2012). Facilitating small groups: how to encourage student learning. *The Clinical Teacher*, 9, 3–8. DOI: 10.1111/j.1743-498X.2011.00493.x

Koenig, Thomas W. MD; Parrish, Samuel K. MD; Terregino, Carol A. MD; Williams, Joy P.; Dunleavy, Dana M. PhD; Volsch, Joseph M. MPA. (2013). Core Personal Competencies Important to Entering Students' Success in Medical School: What Are They and How Could They Be Assessed Early in the Admission Process?. *Academic Medicine*, 88(5), 603–613. DOI: 10.1097/ACM.0b013e31828b3389

McArthur, J. (2022) Rethinking authentic assessment: work, well-being, and society. *Higher Education*. DOI: 10.1007/s10734-022-00822-y

Miah, J., Haque, E., & Thampy, H. (2020). Diversity training for medical students: evaluating impact. *Education for Primary Care*, 31(1), 54–56. DOI: 10.1080/14739879.2019.1691470

Ritter, B. A., Small, E. E., Mortimer, J. W., & Doll, J. L. (2018). Designing Management Curriculum for Workplace Readiness: Developing Students' Soft Skills. *Journal of Management Education*, 42(1), 80–103. DOI: 10.1177/1052562917703679

Ruggs, E. & Hebl, M. (2012) Diversity, Inclusion, and Cultural Awareness for Classroom and Outreach Education. In B. Bogue & E. Cady (Eds.). *Apply Research to Practice (ARP) Resources*. Retrieved [22/12/2022] from <http://www.engr.psu.edu/AWE/ARPResources.aspx>

Woolston, C. (2021). Discrimination still plagues science. *Nature*, 600(7887), 177–179. DOI: 10.1038/d41586-021-03043-y

A foundation module in Tourism & Hospitality reconfigured to embrace notions of sustainability, inclusivity and decolonization

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Clare Stephens

Subject Coordinator and Senior Lecturer, Oxford Brookes University
cstephens@brookes.ac.uk

Graham Van Wyk

Oxford Brookes University, Lecturer
gvanwyk@brookes.ac.uk

This article outlines changes made to a business- focused Foundation module in Tourism and Hospitality taught at Oxford Brookes University in order to make it more multi-disciplinary. Notions of decolonization, inclusivity and sustainability were embraced in line with wider university agendas and the authors' own backgrounds and concerns. This article describes the initial changes made to the module, but it should be noted that this is a work in progress and further changes are planned. However, the authors' discovered that even small adjustments/additions to a module can impact the students' experience and world-view significantly.

Introduction

Tourism and Hospitality (T&H) has become an increasingly contested industry, facing a range of challenges. The movement of people as a result of climate change, the industry's contribution to global warming as a result of dependence on fossil fuels and the increased regulatory restrictions on crossing borders have made many reconsider the standard practices and expectations in the industry, from both an entrepreneurial and consumer perspective. As a consequence, the academic study of T&H also needs a reboot.

With this in mind, when the authors took over the teaching of a Foundation module in 2020, a measure of trepidation took hold. This was a module that had previously been taught by Ph.D. students in the International Hospitality Management Department at Oxford Brookes University focusing primarily on the economic value of T&H to a country with only a nod to sustainability issues. There was hardly any mention of decolonization or inclusivity. The authors' combined backgrounds in Economics, Anthropology and EAP meant that whilst continuing with the business aspects of the module, it was also incumbent to add a social science perspective to the module, all knowledge being viewed as contestable. As Shepherd (2002) notes, tourists may view cultural experiences as sacred and

economic transactions as profane, but the two are in fact inextricably linked. This was alongside the need to update the module in line with the university's concern for inclusivity, decolonization and sustainability (from the IDEAS framework).

Teaching Tourism and Hospitality is well-placed in a programme of study to enable students to encounter these thoughts in an academic context that is appropriate to foundation studies. In addition to developing academic literacy in written and spoken communication, T&H also validates 'experience' (the experience of the tourist) and raises the issue of the 'cultural bias' of perceptions (when encountering the 'other').

Education for sustainable development and decolonization projects

The taking over of the module coincided with two Oxford Brookes Business school initiatives, one being to embed the Advance HE Education for Sustainable Development Competencies and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in all Foundation modules starting with our Learning Outcomes (LOs) (D'Abreu, 2021). The other was a PETAL (Peer Enhancement of Teaching and Learning) Project on Decolonization. These initiatives required some quite dramatic changes to the inherited module.